

THIOKETONIC ESTERS. PART VI.

By S. K. MITRA.

The condensation of aldehydes with β -thioketonic esters has resulted in the formation of β -trithioaldehydes. A mechanism of the reaction has been suggested. The β -thioketonic esters react in the thiol phase.

The reaction of benzaldehyde with ethyl thioacetoacetate in the presence of acid condensing agent furnished β -trithiobenzaldehyde (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 633). The reaction is characteristic of β -thioketonic esters and this has now been confirmed. It is also important to note that the reaction could not be performed in a perfectly anhydrous condition, the presence of moisture was essential. This suggests that aldehydes at first form additive compounds hydroxysulphides (I) with β -thioketonic esters in thiol phase, which owing to their unstability (*vide* Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 76) give rise to hydroxymercaptans (II) in the presence of mineral acids. These hydroxymercaptans then lose water intramolecularly to form stable trithio derivatives (III).

(R = H, alkyl or aryl).

A similar mechanism can be suggested for the formation of β -trithio derivatives from the interaction of hydrogen sulphide with aldehydes (Fromm and Baumann, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2600; 1901, 24, 1431, 1457; 1900, 23, 60).

Similarly, trithioformaldehyde (V) was obtained by the hydrolysis of the compound (IV), furnished by the condensation of chloromethylether with sodioethyl thioacetacetate :

The results of the reaction of β -thioketonic esters with aldehydes have been given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Esters.	$\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CHO}$.	$\text{H}\cdot\text{CHO}$.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OMe})\text{CHO}$. (1:4)	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{OH})(\text{OMe})\cdot\text{CHO}$. (1:3:4)
$\text{Me}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{CH}(\text{Me})\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$	$(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CHS})_3$	$(\text{CH}_2\text{S})_3$	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OMe})\text{CHS}]_3$	$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{OH}\cdot\text{OMeCHS})_3$
	m. p. 226°	m. p. 218°	m. p. 186°	m. p. 220° (decomp.)
$\text{Me}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ $\text{Me}_2\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}_2$	Do	Do	—	Do
$\text{SC}:(\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et})_2$	Do	—	—	Do
$\text{Me}\cdot\text{CS}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ CO_2Et	—	—	Do	—

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Aldehydes with β -Thioketonic Esters (General Method).

The β -thioketonic ester was dissolved in ethyl alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0°. The aldehyde together with a few drops

of water were next added to the mixture which was for a short time kept at 100° and left overnight. The products were identified with those obtained by the interaction of hydrogen sulphide with the corresponding aldehydes, dissolved in alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride.

β-Trithiobenzaldehyde.—Ethyl methylthioacetate (5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (20 c.c.) containing benzaldehyde (4 g.). The product was isolated as needles from acetic acid, m.p. 226°. It was also isolated in a similar manner from a mixture of ethyl isobutylthioacetate (3 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 g.).

β-Trithioanisaldehyde.—Ethyl methylthioacetate (5 g.) in alcohol (10 c. c.) was mixed with anisaldehyde (3 g.). The compound was isolated as needles from acetic acid, m. p. 186°. [Found : C, 63·0 ; H, 5·6. (C₈H₈OS)₃ requires C, 63·1 ; H, 5·3 per cent].

The same compound was isolated from a mixture of diethylthioacetone-dicarboxylate (3 g.) and anisaldehyde (2 g.) as also from a mixture of diethyl thioacetylmalonate (2 g.) and anisaldehyde (2 g.).

β-Trithiovanillin.—Ethyl methylthioacetate (4 g.) was mixed with a solution of vanillin (4 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.). The compound was isolated as needles from pyridine, m.p. 220°. [Found : C, 56·8 ; H, 4·6. (C₈H₈O₂S)₃ requires C, 57·1 ; H, 4·7 per cent].

The same compound was isolated from a mixture of ethyl isobutylthioacetate (2 g.) and vanillin (2 g.) as also from a mixture of diethyl thioacetone-dicarboxylate (5 g.) and vanillin (3 g.).

Trithioformaldehyde.—Aqueous formaldehyde (10 c.c. of 40% solution) was added to a solution of ethyl methylthioacetate (10 g.) in ethyl alcohol (40 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride. The whole mass was kept at the room temperature for 4 hours. The precipitate furnished colourless needles from acetic acid, m.p. 218°. [Found : S, 68·8. (CH₂S)₃ requires S, 69·5 per cent].

The same compound was isolated from a mixture of ethyl isobutylthioacetate (2 g.) and aqueous formaldehyde (5 c.c.).

Ethyl β-Methylmethoxymercapto-α-methylcrotonate.—Ethyl thioacetate (33 g.) was added slowly under ice cooling to emulsified sodium (5 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.) suspension. The mixture was kept at room temperature (15°) for 3 hours and chloromethylether (10 g.) was slowly added. The mixture was boiled under reflux (6 hours). From the benzene extract the fraction, b.p. 120°/12 mm. was collected. (Found : C, 50·3 ; H, 7·5 ; S, 16·6. C₈H₁₄O₂S requires C, 50·5 ; H, 7·3 ; S, 16·8 per cent).

Trithioformaldehyde from Ethyl β -Methylmethoxymercapto- α -methylcrotonate.—Ethyl β -methylmethoxymercapto- α -methylcrotonate (5 g.) was mixed with aqueous hydrobromic acid (d 1.87, 30 c.c.) at room temperature (15°). After 2 hours the mixture was kept at 50° (4 hours). The product was then diluted to twice its volume with water and the separated material was washed with alcohol. The residue furnished trithioformaldehyde from pyridine, m.p. 218° .

My sincere thanks are due to Prof. Samuel Smiles, F.R.S. for his keen interest in this investigation and also for the facilities granted.

KING'S COLLEGE,
LONDON.

Received March 1, 1938.
